

Supporting information

File name	Description
Suppl_Text.pdf	Text S1. Protologues of the new <i>Bifidobacteriaceae</i> taxa.
Suppl_Tables.xlsx	Table S1. Metagenomes of <i>Bifidobacteriaceae</i> used in this study and the accession numbers of the 16S rRNA genes recovered from the datasets. Table S2. Genome characteristics of the <i>Bifidobacteriaceae</i> genomes used in this study. Table S3. Analysis of the CAZymes encoded by the MAGs of termite-associated <i>Bifidobacteriaceae</i> . Table S4. Samples used in the 16S rRNA diversity study and recovered 16S rRNA gene phylotypes. Table S5. Relative abundance of different lineages of <i>Bifidobacteriaceae</i> in bacterial amplicon libraries of flagellate suspensions and whole gut (WG) samples of termites and cockroaches. Table S6. Taxon-specific gene markers identified by CheckM v.1. in the type species of <i>Bifidobacteriaceae</i> (isolates) and the termite-specific lineages (MAGs).

Suppl_Figures.pdf **Fig.S1** Phylogenomic tree of *Bifidobacteriaceae*, including low-quality MAGs.

Fig. S2 Phylogeny of the bifunctional phosphoketolase (Xfp) of termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* (TAB) and other family members, and the homologous monofunctional phosphoketolases (Xpk) of *Actinomycetota* and other bacterial phyla.

Fig. S3 PTS system for *N*-acetyl-glucosamine (A) and glucose/mannose (B) and their conversion to fructose 6-phosphate in termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae*.

Fig. S4 Phylogeny of the organophosphate antiporter (OPA) of termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* (TAB) and their closest relatives from public reference databases.

Fig. S5 Phylogeny of Group A [FeFe] hydrogenases in the genus *Ancillula* and *Opitulatrix* and their homologs in public databases.

Fig. S6 Phylogeny of PFOR in termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* and their homologs from public databases.

Fig. S7 Enzymes of asparagine biosynthesis encoded by termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* and other family members.

Fig. S8 Phylogeny of the threonine/serine exporter (ThrE) of termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* and its homologs in public databases.

Fig. S9 Enzymes of murein biosynthesis encoded by termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* and other family members.

Fig. S10 Elements of different DNA repair mechanisms encoded by *Bifidobacteriaceae* and other *Actinomycetales*.

Fig. S11 Phylogeny of the folate transporter (FolT) encoded by members of the genus *Ancillula* and its homologs from public databases.

Fig. S12 Expanded biosynthetic pathways for amino acid (A) and cofactor (B) biosynthesis in the *Ancillula* and *Opitulatrix* MAGs.
